

THE ROLE OF THE EXPERIENCES OF THE UNITED STATES AND EUROPEAN COUNTRIES IN THE ORGANIZATION OF LAW ENFORCEMENT ACTIVITIES

Xidirov Furqat Shukrullayevich

Senior lecturer of the Institute of advanced training of the Ministry of internal affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12515611>

Annotation: this article studied the experiences of the US and European countries in the organization of the activities of law enforcement agencies and developed suggestions and recommendations by the author.

Keywords: law enforcement area, police departments, Self-Government, Municipal Structures.

Today, the organization and coordination of the Prevention of violations in the US and European countries is carried out by the police departments for states, cities and individual territories. At the same time there are separate municipal police structures, and since the indivisibility of law enforcement functions restricts the right to self-government in the independent solution of issues within the local framework, it is proposed to give the powers of maintaining public order directly to municipal structures[1].

That being said, such a procedure is reflected in the services of the US Sheriff. In the United States, the task of ensuring public order and safety in administrative areas is largely assigned to sheriffs. The sheriff (Eng. "Sheriff") was an official of the police performing certain administrative functions in their county in the United States[2], in the early days they used their service in the counties in the interests of the King. And now sheriffs are officers of the police with broad powers to ensure public order and safety in administrative areas, prevention of offenses, fight crime and execution of penalties[3].

The sheriff is a person fully responsible for the state of public order in the service area and has a somewhat independent, wide range of rights and powers in his activities. Its activities are financed by the local budget[4]. The role of the sheriff's service in the country's Hmqos system is so great that their provision of legitimacy – equated to the provision of constitutions in some states, the legal status of sheriffs is clearly defined in the Constitutions of some. In general, the sheriff is the "peace-keeper" in many counties, at the same time, the principal official in the county.

In addition to the use of the support of all male citizens in the county in the elimination of mass unrest and detention, the investigation of crimes, patrolling, control of road safety, the responsibility for the condition of municipal stands is clearly shown how wide the scope of its powers is[5]. In the U.S. police, sheriffs are appointed in different states in different order for a term of 4-6 years. In particular, in the administrative regions of Rhode Island, Hawaii, they are personally appointed by the governor. In California, it is established that while employees with a four-year seniority in the law enforcement system are assigned to the position, individuals who run for sheriff in Idaho, Mississippi, Oklahoma, Kansas are required to undergo a special training course. In some administrative areas of the state, notably Iowa City, the sheriff is empowered to directly appoint and release his or her assistants and other responsible staff in conducting service activities[6].

American experts who have studied the role and importance of PPX employees in the system of ensuring public order and safety in residential areas in the country recognize this service as the "heart, core of the police" [2]. Since the decentralized police system in the United States has decided, there is no uniformity in the forms of Organization of PPX activities in the country.

The US police has a decentralized system, the Russian scientist D.D. Shalyagin considers this to be the result of the historical formation of statehood on the territory of North American States, and shows the main difference of this system from the police systems of European states when it was founded on the principle of "bottom to Top" [7]. There are more than 40,000 police agencies in the United States, and the country does not have a Central Police Office coordinating their management. In the United States, the tasks of maintaining public order and ensuring security, combating crime are mainly assigned to the States [2]. Many of the U.S. police agencies are sheriff's offices located in the States, and more than three thousand in the county [8]. The number of State and local police plots in the country is 18,789, 13,578 of which are general-order local police units, 3,088 are sheriff's offices, 49 are state units, and the remaining 1,316 are local and State Special Jurisdiction units (port Police, Traffic Police, etc.). The number of policeholders who take the oath, working on a full-time job in the country, is 2.4 per 1,000 residents, compared to 2.3 in larger cities [4]. In the US, a very effective information system is decided and operates, providing federal police authorities, state, city and county police with all the necessary information [9]. Legal scholar P.N. Astapenko correctly noted that police bodies in European countries are in constitutional-legal relations: a) an executive authority within a government with special authority; b) participates as a subject of ensuring public order and safety [10].

Another specific system among European countries in the field of ensuring public order and security in administrative regions is decided in Germany. In the German public administration system, the police occupy one of the main places [2], which includes the Federal Police (Bundespolizei), the Federal Office of Criminal Police (Bundeskriminalamt) and the IIVS of the lands (Landespolizei) [11]. The IIVS of the territories unconditionally fulfill the instructions of the Federal IIV, while the Federal IIV cannot interfere with the tasks that fall under the competence of the subjects [12]. The system of ensuring public order and security in the country is decentralized, and this activity mainly falls on the responsibility of the country's policies [13].

The lower structures of the German police, which are engaged in ensuring public order and safety in residential areas, are the points of order maintenance. They are different in different places: "general police stations", "police stations", "police stations", "police posts", "police inspectorates", etc. These structures, like their TPS, operate day and night [14]. Analysis of the legal literature and direct studies on the continuation of the tour of Duty carried out in Germany showed that the territorial police included the offices of the police of Order, Criminal, maintaining order in water bodies, mobilization, Constitution guard, and the service is the police of order, which is engaged in ensuring public order and safety.

Although each country of the country adheres to its own legislation and departmental documents, the activities of the order protection police are the same in all regions: to prevent violations and carry out operational-search measures that cannot be delayed until the arrival of the criminal police;

to ensure public order and safety during public events;

to maintain order in public places, to guard structures and government buildings of; control of compliance with fire safety, sanitary and epidemiological and market trade regulations;

control of the passport system;

control of compliance with regulations in gambling houses, lotteries and totalizers;

forest protection; control of compliance in hotels, restaurants, bars and casinos;

implementation of local civil defense;

supervision of minors who remain unattended[15].

In Germany, the person who heads the local government is also the first official of the police organization in the area. Consequently, while some country policies look at the state in whole or in part, some are municipal institutions[16]. The country's Public Order Police Service 160-165 thousand employees.

Ensuring public order and security among European countries, a system with another specific aspect in the field of combating crime, was formed in France.

Historically decentralized like other European countries and subordinated to various institutions of power, the French police today consists of two main central institutions, the National Police and the gendarmerie, United in the IV system[17].

These structures, the lawyer S.N. Shishkarev noted that, formed in the process of long historical progress, it is a professionally militarized structure of the executive branch, which occupies an important place in the French police system, with a clear scope of powers by legislation[18].

The French IIV carries out its activities in two areas. The first of these is direct police activity, while the second is reflected in solving various large-scale problems in the internal affairs, social and administrative sphere.

Therefore, along with leading the activities of the National Police and the Gendarmerie, the IIV also performs a number of socio-political tasks, such as registering political parties and associations in the country, exercising control over the activities of local authorities, ensuring the state's civil protection.

The French National Police is entrusted with all the functions of the police, including the maintenance and safety of public order, the function of combating crime, in order to effectively ensure them, about twenty general departments, departments, centers, institutes and services operate in its structure.

Although the main task of the General Directorate of public security within the French National Police is to directly maintain public order and ensure the safety of citizens, it also performs such tasks as providing assistance to the population in its activities; preventing violations; law enforcement, in particular, the investigation and investigation of crimes related to damage in not large quantities[19].

Also, the tasks of maintaining public order and ensuring the safety of citizens are carried out in a specific order by independent structural structures of the national police, such as the General Directorate of the Border Police, which carries out services in the border areas, railways and air transport areas, the main task – the Central Service of the Republican Security Corps, whose

The municipal police of France, which is provided at the expense of a full local budget, carries out the maintenance and safety of public order in cities and other residential areas, and works in continuous cooperation with the National Police in this regard.

Like the French national IV police, the militarized national gendarmerie, headed by the General Directorate, has an important place in ensuring public safety, ensuring the peace and tranquility of the population. The gendarmerie functions as a police force in rural areas and in smaller towns that make up half of the country's population, 90% of the state's territory. Local gendarmes are very similar in structure and function to the National Police.

Although the French gendarmerie is divided into an departmental gendarmerie specialized in carrying out the investigation and other daily tasks of the police and a mobile Gendarmerie whose main function is to ensure public safety, the country also has a naval gendarmerie, an Air Transport Gendarmerie and an air gendarmerie.

Currently, the Turkish police is part of the system of the Ministry of internal affairs of the Republic, and it contains the Directorate General of security.

The duties of the Turkish police include:

maintaining public order, ensuring the safety of citizens and their property;

identification and prosecution of offenders;

implementation of the Prevention of violations;

perform other tasks set by law, regulations and government regulatory legal documents[20].

There are also political tasks of the police to maintain state unity and ensure constitutional order. In addition, the police also carry out administrative functions, namely security measures and assistance to other bodies.

The protection of internal security and public order in Turkey is carried out by three branches of the police:

1) Directorate-General of the Turkish National Police, responsible for urban areas;

2) general command of the gendarmerie responsible for rural areas;

3) Coastal Security Command protecting the coast of the country[21].

The Directorate General of the Turkish national police is divided into a central organization and territorial units. The central organization has a rather complex structure.

The Turkish police is led by the director general. It is subordinate to seven departments, including the office, the Directorate of press and protocol relations, the Department of intelligence, the Department of special operations, the Department of inspections, the Supervisory Authority and the center of police leaders.

The director-general is assisted by five deputies, each of whom manages several departments. For example, one of the deputies is in charge of the Department of international relations, European affairs, borders and migration and the fight against organized crime.

Turkey is administratively divided into provinces, cities and districts. Turkey has 81 provincial police directorates, 751 municipal police directorates attached to them, 22 border crossing point directorates, 18 free zones with police precincts and 834 police precincts.

The Central Organization of the police is subordinate to the Ministry of internal affairs, as well as in the provinces, the leaders of the police are subordinate to the regional governors and district leaders.

The Turkish gendarmerie is a militarized armed organization that maintains security, law enforcement. It is established and operates under the law "on the organization of the gendarmerie, its duties and powers".

The Gendarmerie is responsible for maintaining security and public order, and also performs other functions prescribed by law.

The Gendarmerie General Command is subordinate to the Ministry of the interior. The area of responsibility of the Gendarmerie is calculated in addition to the areas where the police operate.

The gendarmerie performs four main functions:

1. Administrative-crime prevention, investigation of smuggling cases, investigation and execution of punishment guard the institutions of the Department.
2. Legal-identification, capture and transportation of criminals, presentation of evidence in criminal cases to the relevant authorities.
3. Ensuring compliance with the military law and regulations of the country based on the mandate of the military – supreme command.
4. Other tasks, i.e. the performance of laws, statutes and other tasks set out in government warrants[22].

The general command system of the gendarmerie includes its headquarters and units, security units, border units, educational institutions, administrative and material and technical support units.

Coast Guard. The Turkish coast guard was established under the coast guard act of 1982. The Coast Guard performs its duties in the territorial and internal waters of Turkey, the exclusive economic zone and the continental submarine areas.

The Turkish Coast Guard committee carries out tasks such as protecting territorial water security, ensuring the safety of life and property at sea, preventing smuggling activities, carrying out search and rescue operations, preventing pollution of water bodies.

Each of the three branches of the Turkish police has requirements for employees.

The Directorate-General of security of Turkey is made up of the commanding staff of the police (of different ranks) officer staff and staff. The command structure includes the director general of the Turkish police, the 1-4 step superintendent of the police, the inspector general, the inspector, the deputy inspector, the police officers.

It should be noted that the implementation of the Prevention of violations in neighborhoods in Turkey is entrusted to the gendarmerie and the area of responsibility is attached[23].

References:

- 1.Тоболин В.В. Право муниципального управления. – М., 1997. – С. 136.
- 2.Большой юридический словарь / Под ред. А.Я. Сухарева, В.Д. Зоркина, В.Е. Крутских. VI. – М.: Инфра-М, 1997. – С. 766.
- 3.Кваша Л.Ф. Особенности правового статуса шерифа и его значение для правового регулирования деятельности местной милиции // Местное самоуправление: теория и практика. Труды Академии управления. – 1998. – С. 198.
- 4.Собиров М.С., Норов В.И. Поездка в Америку: отчет, впечатления, опыт. – Т., 1991. – С. 6.
- 5.Зиёдуллаев М.З. Аҳоли турар жойларида жамоат тартибини сақлаш ва ҳуқуқбузарликлар профилактикасининг илғор хориж тажрибасини мамлакатимизга жорий этишнинг асосий йўналишлари // Жамият ва бошқарув. – 2016. – № 4. – Б. 178.
- 6.Зиёдуллаев М.З. Аҳоли турар жойларида жамоат тартибини сақлаш тизимлари: тарихи, бугуни ва хориж тажрибаси: Ўқув қўлланма. – Т.: ЎЗР ИИБ Академияси, 2015. –

- Б. 56. 2Hale A.D. Police patrol. – New York, 1981. – P. 2. 3Осипов Ю.И. Организация патрульно-постовой службы местной полиции США: Учеб. пособие. – М., 1990.– С. 15.
- 7.Шалагин Д.Д. Полиция США – организационные и правовые основы деятельности: Автореф. дис. ... канд. юрид. наук. – М., 1998. // [Эл. манба]. – URL: <http://dissercat.com/content/politsiya-ssha-organizatsionnye-ipravovye-osnovy-deyatelnosti> (мур. вақти: 20.05.2016).
- 2Майоров В.И. Организация деятельности по охране общественного порядка в США, странах Европы и России: Учебное пособие. – Челябинск, 2003. – С. 17.
- 8.Кваша Л.Ф. Особенности правового статуса шерифа и его значение для правового регулирования деятельности местной милиции // Местное самоуправление: теория и практика. Труды Академии управления. – 1998. – С. 197. 4Криминология / Под ред. Дж. Ф. Шели; Пер. с англ. – СПб., 2003. – С. 466.
- 9.Полиция зарубежных стран: система организации и опыт профессиональной подготовки кадров: Учебное пособие / Якубов А.С., Асямов С.В., Таджиев А.А., Миразов Д.М. – Т., 2010. – С. 197.
- 10.Астапенко П.Н. Конституционно-правовые основы деятельности полиции (милиции) стран Европейского Союза и Российской Федерации: Автореф. дис. ... докт. юрид. наук. – Москва, 2009. / [Эл. манба]. – URL: <http://www.dissercat.com/content> (мур. вақти: 14.05.2016). 2Административное право зарубежных стран. – М.: СПАРК, 1996. – С. 120.
- 11.Полиция зарубежных стран: система организации и опыт профессиональной подготовки кадров: Учебное пособие / Якубов А.С., Асямов С.В., Таджиев А.А., Миразов Д.М. – Т., 2010. – С. 294.
- 12.Полиция Германии: история и современность: Учеб. пособие. – М.: Академия управления МВД России, 2000. – С. 65.
- 13.Лазерев В.В., Болтенко Ю.Н. Компетенция органов местного самоуправления Гремании в сфере правопорядка // Местное самоуправление: теория и практика. Труды Академии управления. – 1998. – С. 215.
- 14.Зиёдуллаев М.З. Милиция таянч пунктларининг жамоат тартибини сақлаш ва хавфсизлигини таъминлаш фаолиятини бошқаришни такомиллаштириш: юрид. фан. номз... дис. автореф. – Т., 2008. – Б. 230.
- 15.Полиция зарубежных стран: система организации и опыт профессиональной подготовки кадров: Учебное пособие / Якубов А.С., Асямов С.В., Таджиев А.А., Миразов Д.М. – Т., 2010. – С. 323.
- 16.Лазерев В.В., Болтенко Ю.Н. Компетенция органов местного самоуправления Гремании в сфере правопорядка // Местное самоуправление: теория и практика. Труды Академии управления. – 1998. – С. 217. 3Полиция Германии: история и современность: Учеб. пособие. – М.: Академия управления МВД России, 2000. – С. 80.
- 17.Мачковский И.Г. Полиция Франции (организация, кадры, уголовно-процессуальная деятельность). – М., 1972. – С. 24.
- 18.Шишкарёв С.Н. Полицейская система Франции: Автореф. дис. ... канд. юрид. наук. – М., 2001. // [Эл. манба]. – URL: <http://dissercat.com/content/politseiskaya-sistema-frantsii> (мур. вақти: 20.05.2016).
- 19.Полиция зарубежных стран: система организации и опыт профессиональной подготовки кадров: Учебное пособие / Якубов А.С., Асямов С.В., Таджиев А.А., Миразов Д.М. – Т., 2010. – С. 368.

20.<https://eurasianlaw.ru/nashi-rubriki/politsiya-gosudarstv-mira/politsiya-turetskoj-respubliki>

21.<https://eurasianlaw.ru/nashi-rubriki/politsiya-gosudarstv-mira/politsiya-turetskoj-respubliki>

22.<https://eurasianlaw.ru/nashi-rubriki/politsiya-gosudarstv-mira/politsiya-turetskoj-respubliki>

23.<https://eurasianlaw.ru/nashi-rubriki/politsiya-gosudarstv-mira/politsiya-turetskoj-respubliki>

